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Abstract:	This document monitors, analyses, and evaluates all communication and dissemination activities during the first project year of PLATOON (M1-M12), developed as per the communication and dissemination strategy. The main outcome of this deliverable is, that the majority of the communication & dissemination KPIs have been achieved, thus WP9 progressed very well during the first project year, and is now already ahead of the schedule.
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Terms and abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DM	Dissemination Manager
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
EUSEW2020	EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting

H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LI	LinkedIn
PM	Project Manager
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
Q&A	Question & Answer
RE	Restricted
REN	Renewable Energy
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SoMe	Social Media
TM	Technical Manager
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TTP	Tech Transfer Programme
TW	Twitter
VP	Vice President
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
YT	YouTube

Executive Summary

The H2020 PLATOON project (“Digital PLatform and analytics TOols for eNergy”) is an EU-financed project that aims to digitalise the energy sector. PLATOON was launched in January 2020 (M1) and runs until December 2022 (M36). It will research ways to digitalise the energy sector by developing COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing. The project partners will create a digital platform and multiple analytics tools – specifically for the energy sector – that will gather and summarise information from multiple sources (i.e. renewable energy power plants, ESCOs, end users, TSOs, DSOs, etc.), thus helping stakeholders to find and use effectively the most relevant and updated information when being active on the energy market.

The “D9.3 Communication and Dissemination Report” is a deliverable of WP9 “Communication and Dissemination” to be delivered in Month 12 (M12). The aim of this deliverable is to provide an insightful report about the communication and dissemination activities of PLATOON during the first project year as well as the targets and milestones that have been reached within the given time frame. PLATOON followed a widespread set of

dissemination and communication activities in order to communicate the project outcomes to the public, stakeholders, potential users, and experts from the energy industry among others.

Chapter 1 briefly introduces PLATOON and the communication activities that have been made within the first project year. Chapter 2 gives a brief overview of the communication and dissemination strategy, namely the objectives that have been set at the start of the project, the specific target groups as well as the communication and dissemination channels and that have been used to reach various stakeholders. In Chapter 3 there is a detailed monitoring and analysis of the communication and dissemination activities on the website and social media channels, communication and dissemination campaigns, events, open calls, workshops and training, scientific publications as well as industrial dissemination.

Chapter 4 elaborates on the BRIDGE events in which the PLATOON partners took part. Chapter 5 concludes the most important outcomes of the deliverable as well as an outlook for the upcoming two project years. In Chapter 6, two companies give an internal review about this deliverable. And finally, in Chapter 7, we include some project-related references.

1. Introduction

The aim of “D9.3 Communication & Dissemination Report” is to report the progress of WP9 “Communication & Dissemination” of the PLATOON project to the European Commission. The deadline for D9.3 is in December 2020 (M12). Therefore, D9.3 monitors the overall success of the Communication and Dissemination activities for the first project year 2020. The Knowledge and Tech Transfer Department of the Technische Informationsbibliothek Hannover (TIB-KTT)¹ is in charge of **Tasks 9.1 and 9.4 of the WP9 Communication & Dissemination** in the scope of the H2020 PLATOON Project.

At the beginning of the PLATOON project, a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan was developed in D9.1 (due in M3) to communicate the mission, vision, progress, and results of the project to various stakeholders both from the energy sector and beyond. Since then, the project has been visible across the project website, social media channels such as Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, printed materials such as the project brochures, flyers, and stickers, and various marketing campaigns as well as networking during energy online events. Both the online and offline communication and dissemination tools have been substantiated more in detail in D9.2 (due in M4).

The first project year turned out to be very successful for WP9 of the PLATOON project. Since the start of the project in M1, the PLATOON Twitter and LinkedIn accounts experienced a rapid growth in **Twitter (TW) and LinkedIn (LI) followers** as of 7 December 2020 (TW: **630**; LI: **1070**). Also, the project website has been successfully established and promoted via Social Media

¹ The **Knowledge and Tech Transfer Department of TIB (TIB-KTT)** consists of **Alexandra Garatzogianni** and **Michael Fribus**.

(SoMe). Moreover, **6 different PLATOON printed materials** have been created and disseminated both via the website and the SoMe channels. The PLATOON partners visited **32 events²** both online and offline during the first project year. Furthermore, **2 Press Releases** have been published on the PLATOON website and disseminated via SoMe.

Thus, the WP9 has been ahead of the project schedule in the first months of the project already. Moreover, during the first year of the project, various marketing campaigns have been developed and realised which contributed significantly to the degree of awareness of PLATOON. Also, the project partners managed to visit numerous energy fairs and online events.

Overall, the WP9 milestones and KPIs that were set by TIB-KTT at the beginning of the project have been reached and surpassed in M12.

2. Overview of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Objectives

The goal of WP9 Communication & Dissemination is to organise and execute measures to disseminate and communicate the project and the results it will deliver according to the dissemination and communication strategies, defined in D9.1; all with strict alignment to the project IPR principles.

The main objectives of **WP9 (Task 9.1 and Task 9.4)** are:

- Facilitate sharing of knowledge with external, targeted audiences, as well as towards other units of the consortium partners, get feedback from those audiences, and engage them with the project through targeted dissemination activities e.g. presenting at academic and industrial conferences, holding workshops and meetings with developers and engineers, etc.
- Promote visibility of the project and raise awareness about the topics it addresses through effective communication and outreach activities, e.g. publications, the maintenance of the project website, the distribution of printed and electronic material, publication of press releases, etc. The communication and dissemination strategy has been defined in D9.1 in greater detail. It will be refined and continuously improved at both individual-partner and consortium level. The success of the communication and dissemination strategy must be monitored in M12, M24 and M36 (D9.3).

² The **Knowledge & Tech Transfer department of TIB (TIB-KTT)**, consisting of Alexandra Garatzogianni & Michael Fribus, attended **25 events** in total, promoting the PLATOON project.

2.2 Target Groups

Table 1: PLATOON Stakeholder Target Groups

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	BRIEF DESCRIPTION	WHY IS PLATOON INTERESTING TO THEM?	HOW TO ADDRESS THEM?
PLATOON Consortium partners	All 20 partners directly involved in the PLATOON project. Wide range of institutions: enterprises, research institutes, public institutions, etc.	PLATOON is of crucial importance to all Consortium partners as it aligns fully with their organisational goals and strategic direction in the domains of digitalisation and the energy sector in particular	Social Media: YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn (YT, TW, LI), Printed Media, Newsletters, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Website, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform

<p>Energy generation companies/ Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)/ Renewable Energy (REN) Companies</p>	<p>Commercial enterprises that focus on generating electricity, heat, hot water etc., as well as energy services to businesses and private households. Also focus on companies that specialise in renewable energy, green electricity trading and e-mobility.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p> <p>Operation and maintenance of REN power plants, as well as electricity grids can be improved (e.g. easier to foresee upcoming maintenance work, optimised grids thus longer lifespan of those).</p> <p>The project aims to increase the RE share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created which is especially good for start-ups and companies with innovative business models.</p>	<p>Fairs/ Exhibitions, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform</p>
<p>TSOs/ DSOs</p>	<p>Transmission System Operators and Distribution System Operators that operate and maintain electricity and gas grids; those who provide whole local areas or municipalities with energy.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p>	<p>Fairs/ Exhibitions, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform</p>

<p>Small and medium enterprises (SMEs)</p>	<p>Small and medium-sized companies that focus on a business that is very closely linked to the energy sector; e.g. energy-heavy industries such as the automotive sector, mechanical engineering sector, pharma sector, construction sector etc.</p> <p>Especially those companies that have innovative and future-oriented business models.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p> <p>The project aims to increase the REN share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created, and this could be a chance for industries that could provide these with services, goods, know-how etc.</p>	<p>Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Live Sessions, Trainings, Workshops, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform</p>
<p>Energy End Users/ Building owners</p>	<p>Businesses and private households that consume energy. Also, those households/ businesses in focus that possess a REN plant in their homes, or those who want to buy eco power.</p>	<p>Easier access to cheaper, more digitised and sustainable energy.</p> <p>A more decentralised energy system can be created that lowers costs for the energy users and interconnects households with each other (esp. via smart grids); energy security could be improved.</p> <p>Increased energy efficiency for buildings, offices etc. leading to significant cost savings.</p>	<p>Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Printed Media, Specific Communication Campaigns, PLATOON community on FBA platform</p>

<p>EU</p>	<p>Political instances of the EC that represent the interests of the European Union.</p>	<p>Increasing the REN share to reach the ambitious 2050 emissions goals.</p> <p>Help to create an inter-European energy grid that is better interconnected and much less dependent on fossil fuels (thus energy supply security on EU-level could be increased).</p>	<p>Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Specific Communication Campaigns</p>
<p>Municipalities</p>	<p>Cities, settlements or communes that are responsible for certain local/ national/ European areas.</p>	<p>Energy efficiency, optimised energy asset management and social welfare are key priorities of all municipalities and policy makers.</p> <p>Moreover, PLATOON addresses other topics such as smart cities, which are highly relevant</p>	<p>Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Press releases, Newsletter and Project Communication Material</p>
<p>Universities and Research centres</p>	<p>Public and private research and educational institutions that focus on providing people with constantly improving and up-to-date knowledge.</p>	<p>The project results/ milestone results are an important input that could enable universities and research centres to exchange knowledge, technology, data etc. and provide other stakeholders with</p>	<p>Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed media, PLATOON community on FBA platform</p>

		valuable information (f.e. other scientific institutes, companies, etc.).	
General public	All private persons that are generally interested in energy, REN, data science, ecology etc.	<p>The general public, i.e. private persons could be potentially interested in up-to-date energy related topics such as REN, climate change, energy supply security, smart grids, and smart cities a.o.</p> <p>PLATOON addresses the interests of the general public due to the broad range of the topics that the project deals with. Thus, it can engage citizens who are not directly linked to the energy sector to engage themselves into energy topics and become proactive.</p>	Fairs, Social Media (esp. TW, YT), General Communication Campaigns, Printed Media
Funding agencies	Commercial enterprises and public institutions (f.e. Economic development companies) that are providing start-ups, SMEs and projects on EU level with know-how and financial resources.	<p>Funding agencies focus on state-of-the-art developments in their sector.</p> <p>PLATOON being an innovative project funded by the EC, will make sure to communicate its output to funding agencies in relevant domains.</p>	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Specific Communication

			Campaigns, Live Sessions ³ , Workshops, Trainings, PLATOON community on FBA platform
Technological Platforms & Professional Associations and Initiatives	Public platforms that focus on technology-based topics such as Big Data, data Science etc. Example: Leibniz-Gemeinschaft.	PLATOON implements the digitalisation of the energy sector. Its use cases and pilots are highly relevant to related platforms and associations in terms of technology transfer, state of the art and lessons learned which can spur further synergies.	Journals, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Newsletters, Live Sessions ⁴ , Workshops, Trainings, PLATOON community on FBA platform

³ The word “webinars” has been replaced by the term “live sessions”.

⁴ See above.

2.3 Communication Channels and Tools

2.3.1 Website and Social Media

Both the website and the social media channels are the main dissemination tools of the PLATOON project.

The **PLATOON website** is a cross-cutting online channel which hosts key information, e.g. press releases, blog posts, interviews, a brief project description, a page dedicated to the pilots of PLATOON, an introduction of each PLATOON consortium partner among others.

Social Media (SoMe) channels such as Twitter⁵, LinkedIn⁶ or YouTube⁷ are used to share experience and participate in conversations about the progress of the project and disseminate project results and outcomes. Here, a simpler language is used in order to attract people who are less familiar with energy-related or technical topics. Moreover, SoMe such as Twitter and LinkedIn were used to redirect visitors to the website. Also, a PLATOON YouTube channel has been created to disseminate video material of the H2020 energy project.

In less than a year, the **PLATOON LinkedIn** account generated over **1000** followers, while the **PLATOON Twitter** account crossed the **600**-followers-mark.

2.3.2 Online & Offline Events

During the first year of the project, the PLATOON partners visited a broad range of either energy events or similar energy-related, technology, sustainability, ecology, business or climate events. Online events offered an excellent opportunity to participate in relevant energy-related events without being present physically in the event. During these online events, the TIB-KTT department made a great networking effort, i.e. connecting with relevant stakeholders and encouraging them to follow PLATOON on SoMe.

All the visited online and offline events had the focus on the energy sector and were mostly attended by technical stakeholders. However, there were also events on sustainability in a broader sense as well as on digitalisation and technologies related to the digital transformation. These events attracted stakeholders from NGOs, ecological institutions, EU institutions with focus on sustainability as well as ICT companies, technology providers, start-ups and accelerators.

In total, the PLATOON partners visited **32 events**⁸, both offline and online, from M1 to M12.

⁵ https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU

⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/platoon-h2020/>

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWK6cuUlkW53Ap26QggXTvA/about>

⁸ Of which the **TIB-KTT** department visited **25 events** in total, as of 7 December 2020.

2.3.3 Other Communication & Dissemination Activities

Other communication & dissemination tools such as the PLATOON printed materials have been created in the first project year to exploit the H2020 PLATOON project, namely its mission, its vision and its goals. For this, the TIB-KTT prepared 2 different posters in sizes A1 and A4 each, 1 flyer, 1 banner and 2 different stickers. In total, **6 different types of printed materials** were created for the PLATOON project. All of them included info about the PLATOON project for different stakeholder groups from the energy sector and beyond. Here, the stickers and banners were visual materials to catch the attention of potential interested parties, while the posters and the flyer included more detailed info on the project itself.

3. Communication and Dissemination Analysis & Results Monitoring

3.1 Website

The official PLATOON website⁹ of the H2020 PLATOON project has been designed to disseminate the project mission, vision, milestones & further info about the project. Besides the homepage (see Figures 1 - 3 below), there are 8 more pages displayed in the top bar of the PLATOON website:

- **“About PLATOON”**, containing a general overview, scope and objectives, approach, expected results, the PLATOON Consortium, stakeholders, among other items.
- **“Open Calls”**, a page specifically dedicated to the PLATOON open calls that will be launched from M13 on.
- **“News & Events”**, containing blog posts re. the events visited by the PLATOON partners, interviews of the PLATOON representatives, press releases in various languages, among other items.
- **“Platform”**, presenting the PLATOON platform itself, as well as printed materials, deliverables, among other items
- **“Pilots”**, containing a general overview as well as info pages about each of the 7 PLATOON pilots.
- **“Network”**, presenting the Associated Partners Programme, Ambassadors, Technology Transfer Programme, Mentoring Committee, Accelerated SMEs & Start-ups and other related projects.
- **“Ethics & Security”**, containing the legal info and aspects re. the website of the H2020 PLATOON project.
- **“Contact”**, indicating the Coordinator and the WP9 leads as contacts people displayed on the website.

Figure 1: PLATOON Website - Homepage (Part 1)

⁹ PLATOON Website: <https://platoon-project.eu/>

Figure 2: PLATOON Website - Homepage (Part 2)

Figure 3: PLATOON Website - Homepage (Part 3)

Figure 4: PLATOON Website - Interviews section

Figure 5: PLATOON Website - News section

3.1.1 Press Releases

In the first project year (M1-M12), 2 PLATOON Press Releases have been published and promoted via PLATOON's SoMe accounts, as well as by the networks of all Consortium partners and CORDIS.

The first PLATOON Press Release has been published on the **project website** in M5 in **nine (9) different languages of Consortium partners and beyond: English¹⁰, German¹¹, Spanish¹²,**

¹⁰ <https://platoon-project.eu/press-release-digitalising-the-energy-sector-with-disruptive-technologies-how-platoon-brings-a-digital-platform-and-analytics-tools-to-the-industry/>

¹¹ <https://platoon-project.eu/pressemitteilung-digitalisierung-des-energiesektors-mit-bahnbrechenden-technologien-wie-platoon-eine-digitale-plattform-und-analyse-tools-auf-den-energiemarkt-bringt/>

¹² <https://platoon-project.eu/nota-de-prensa-digitalizacion-del-sector-energetico-impulsada-por-tecnologias-disruptivas-platoon-introduce-una-plataforma-digital-y-nuevas-herramientas-de-analisis-en-la-industria/>

French¹³, Russian¹⁴, Serbian¹⁵, Basque¹⁶, Italian¹⁷, and Dutch¹⁸. Each of the different press release versions has been promoted on the PLATOON Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, incl. a brief abstract from the PR as well as a link leading to the press release in the corresponding language.

Figure 6: Poste Italiane promoted PLATOON on their website and SoMe channels

The second PLATOON Press Release has been published in M10, and presented the launch of the [PLATOON Online Community](#) on the FBA platform. On the **PLATOON website**, **English¹⁹**

¹³ <https://platoon-project.eu/communique-de-presse-numeriser-le-secteur-de-lenergie-avec-des-technologies-de-rupture-comment-platoon-apporte-une-plate-forme-numerique-et-des-outils-danalyse-a-lindustrie/>

¹⁴ <https://platoon-project.eu/%d0%bf%d1%80%d0%b5cc-%d1%80%d0%b5%d0%bb%d0%b8%d0%b7-%d0%be%d1%86%d0%b8%d1%84%d1%80%d0%be%d0%b2%d0%ba%d0%b0-%d1%8d%d0%bd%d0%b5%d1%80%d0%b3%d0%b5%d1%82%d0%b8%d1%87%d0%b5%d1%81%d0%ba%d0%be%d0%b3%d0%be/>

¹⁵ <https://platoon-project.eu/saopstenje-digitalizacija-energetskog-sektora-koriscenjem-tehnologija-sa-visokim-potencijalom-za-unosenje-promena-u-konvencionalne-pristupe-kako-platoon-koristi-digitalnu-platformu-i-analiticke-se/>

¹⁶ <https://platoon-project.eu/prentsa-oharra-energia-sektorearen-digitalizazioa-teknologia-disruptiboen-bultzadaz-platoonek-plataforma-digitala-eta-azterketarako-tresnak-txertatu-ditu-industrian/>

¹⁷ <https://platoon-project.eu/comunicato-stampa-digitalizzare-il-settore-energetico-con-technologie-rivoluzionarie-platoon-offre-una-piattaforma-digitale-e-strumenti-di-analisi-per-il-settore-industriale/>

¹⁸ <https://platoon-project.eu/persbericht-digitalisering-van-de-energiesector-aan-de-hand-van-baanbrekende-technologieen-hoe-platoon-een-digitaal-platform-en-analysetools-naar-de-industrie-brengt/>

¹⁹ <https://platoon-project.eu/press-release-platoon-an-h2020-project-that-brings-a-digital-platform-and-analytics-tools-to-the-energy-sector-launches-its-online-community/>

and **German**²⁰ versions of the second PR have been published. Besides the PLATOON website, it has been published both on the website of **TIB** (see Figure 7) and of **FBA** (see Figure 8) in **English**^{21,22} and **German**^{23,24} respectively. Moreover, the PR has been published on the website of **PI** in **English** and **Italian**.

Figure 7: Promotion of the second PLATOON Press Release on the TIB website

Figure 8: Promotion of the second PLATOON Press Release on the FBA website

²⁰ <https://platoon-project.eu/pressemitteilung-platoon-ein-h2020-projekt-das-eine-digitale-plattform-und-analysetools-fur-den-energiesektor-zur-verfugung-stellt-ruft-eine-eigene-online-community-ins-leben/>

²¹ <https://blogs.tib.eu/wp/tib/2020/10/06/platoon-launches-its-online-community/>

²² <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/platoon-news-events-articles-more/5f7776b4f9a7a75c28f356ae>

²³ <https://blogs.tib.eu/wp/tib/2020/10/06/platoon-ruft-eigene-online-community-ins-leben/>

²⁴ <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/platoon-news-events-articles-more/5f7bae8ff9a7a75c28f35902>

On Twitter and LinkedIn, the publication of the second PLATOON Press Release has been promoted in **English, German, French, Russian, Spanish, Brazilian Portuguese, EU Portuguese, Greek, and Italian** as can be seen in Figure 9 below.

The upcoming third Press Release of the PLATOON project is planned to be published in M13 (i.e. January 2021), and the topic will be the launch of the PLATOON Open Calls.

Figure 9: Promotion of the 2nd PLATOON Press Release on TW in various languages
(English, German, French, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian, Russian, Greek)

3.2 Social Media

3.2.1 Twitter

The PLATOON TW account²⁵ has been used to attract the general public that were interested in topics such as energy, sustainability, efficiency, innovation, digitalisation, among others. Nevertheless, TW could also attract stakeholders that were directly involved in the energy sector, as well as TW accounts of the different DGs of the European Commission. Because of the character restriction for each post, the tweets were shorter, and the language was easier than f.e. on LI. The **biggest follower growth** of the PLATOON TW account could be achieved in June/July (M6-M7)²⁶ especially during the EUSEW2020 events, and in October²⁷ (M10).

3.2.1.1 Twitter Statistics January - June 2020 (M1-M6)

Figure 10: PLATOON Twitter Stats January 2020 (M1)

²⁵ https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU

²⁶ See Figures 16 and 17 on pages 32 and 34.

²⁷ See Figure 20 on page 37.

Figure 11: Most successful PL Tweets (M1-M12)

Figure 12: PLATOON Twitter Stats February 2020 (M2)

Figure 13: PLATOON Twitter Stats March 2020 (M3)

Figure 14: PLATOON Twitter Stats April 2020 (M4)

Figure 15: PLATOON Twitter Stats May 2020 (M5)

Figure 16: PLATOON Twitter Stats June 2020 (M6)

Table 2: PLATOON Twitter Stats M1 - M6 (incl. time before project start in 2019)

	2019 ²⁸	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
Tweets	-	1	16	29	27	37	64
Impressions	-	2,320	28.6K	54.9K	54.7K	54.5K	61.9K
Profile Visits	75	205	1,717	2,194	1,909	2,566	3,193
Mentions	-	2	13	11	17	27	48
New Followers	9	21	41	29	54	53	85

²⁸ Time before the official start of the H2020 PLATOON project in M1 (January 2020).

3.2.1.2 Twitter Statistics July - December 2020 (M7-M12)

Figure 17: PLATOON Twitter Stats July 2020 (M7)

Figure 18: PLATOON Twitter Stats August 2020 (M8)

Figure 19: PLATOON Twitter Stats September 2020 (M9)

SEP 2020 SUMMARY

Tweets	29	Tweet impressions	43K
Profile visits	1,990	Mentions	29
New followers	47		

Figure 20: PLATOON Twitter Stats October 2020 (M10)

Figure 21: PLATOON Twitter Stats November 2020 (M11)

Figure 22: PLATOON Twitter Stats December 2020 (M12) as of 4.12.2020

Figure 23: PLATOON Twitter Account on 18.11.2020 - 600 Followers reached

PLATOON #DigitalEnergy Project
 @PLATOON_EU

@EU_H2020 project digitalising the #energy sector w/ the adoption of data analytics, edge computing, AI & #IDSA. Comm by @AlexandraGaratz & @FribusMichael

Hanover, Lower Saxony | platoon-project.eu | Joined October 2019

475 Following 601 Followers

Table 3: PLATOON Twitter Stats M7 - M12

	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 ²⁹
Tweets	42	25	29	45	25	6
Impressions	57.7K	39.1K	43K	65.7K	45.9K	12.2K
Profile Visits	2,165	1,365	1,990	4,418	4,632	726
Mentions	28	22	29	53	40	7
New Followers	88	45	47	66	51	9

²⁹ The PLATOON Consortium decided on a submission date of the D9.3 on 18 December 2020. In the table, the data for M12 have been included on 7 December 2020. Therefore, the complete statistics for M12 will be presented in greater detail in D9.4 (due M26).

Table 4: PLATOON Twitter Stats for the First Project Year 2020 (M1 - M12)

Twitter Stats	TOTAL (M1 - M12 ³⁰)
Tweets	346
Impressions	520.5K
Profile Visits	27.1K
Mentions	297
Total Number of Followers	598 ³¹

3.2.2 LinkedIn

The PLATOON LI company page³² has been used to attract businesspersons and experts, esp. from the energy domain. Since there were no character restrictions, the posts on LI were longer and more detailed than the Tweets. Also, more technical terms were used on LI. Similarly, as on TW, the biggest follower growth could be achieved in June-July (M6-M7)³³, esp. during the EUSEW events, and in October (M10)³⁴. The reason for the rapid follower growth of the PLATOON LI account during this summer was the successful networking on the EUSEW 2020 platform. Moreover, the profiles of the participants on the EUSEW 2020 platform were often connected to their LI business profiles. This made it easier to interconnect with them on LI during and after the EUSEW2020 events.

³⁰ The PLATOON Consortium decided on a submission date of the D9.3 on 18 December 2020. In the table, the data for M12 have been included on 7 December 2020. Therefore, the complete statistics for M12 will be presented in greater detail in D9.4 (due M26).

³¹ Please note that we used the numbers from the TW Stats M1-M12 as of 7 December 2020. **In fact, the number of total TW followers is higher: currently 630 followers.**

³² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/platoon-h2020/>

³³ See Figure 34 on page 47.

³⁴ See Figure 42 on page 53.

Figure 24: Most Successful LI Posts (M1-M12)

3.2.2.1 LinkedIn Statistics January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 25: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Page Views, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 26: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Unique Visitors, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 27: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Impressions, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 28: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Unique Impressions, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 29: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Clicks, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 30: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Reactions, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 31: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Comments, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 32: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Shares, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 33: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, Engagement Rate, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Figure 34: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats, New Followers, January - June 2020 (M1 - M6)

Table 5: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats M1 - M6 (incl. time before project start)

	2019	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
VISITORS							
Page Views	11	60	66	153	311	240	1,017
Unique Visitors	7	20	30	59	101	90	318
UPDATES							
Impressions	-	-	-	1,529	2,275	3,925	9,561
Unique Impressions	-	-	-	587	1,018	1,445	2,821
Clicks	-	-	-	67	65	157	203
Reactions	-	-	-	88	130	201	340
Comments	-	-	-	-	-	3	22
Shares	-	-	-	18	30	51	133
Engagement Rate	-	-	-	11.31%	9.89%	10.5%	7.3%
FOLLOWERS							
New Followers	2	7	7	13	22	35	213

3.2.2.2 LinkedIn Statistics July - December 2020 (M7 - M12)

Figure 35: PLATOON LinkedIn Account on 17 July 2020

Figure 36: Stats of the PLATOON LinkedIn Account on 17 July 2020

Figure 37: LI Followers by Industries, 2 October 2020

Figure 38: LI Followers by Locations, 2 October 2020

Figure 39: LI Followers by Job Functions, 2 October 2020

Figure 40: PLATOON LinkedIn Account on 18.11.2020 - First 1,000 Followers reached

Figure 41: Post re. 1000 followers on the PLATOON LinkedIn account

Table 6: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats (M7 - M12)

	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 ³⁵
VISITORS						
Page Views	749	333	579	661	417	100
Unique Visitors	231	128	220	213	151	40
UPDATES						
Impressions	10,178	5,286	6,908	10,799	9,078	2469
Unique Impressions	4,287	2,464	3,293	5,452	4,457	1,143
Clicks	391	146	161	257	191	42
Reactions	314	183	255	433	338	71
Comments	7	6	10	7	15	6
Shares	65	61	69	140	66	20
Engagement Rate	7.63%	7.49%	7.17%	7.75%	6.72%	6.87%
FOLLOWERS						
New Followers	185	119	144	166	116	42

³⁵ The PLATOON Consortium decided on a submission date of the D9.3 on 18 December 2020. In the table, the M12 stats have been added on 7 December 2020. Therefore, the complete LinkedIn statistics for M12 will be presented in greater detail in D9.4 (due M26).

Table 7: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for the First Project Year 2020 (M1 - M12)

	TOTAL (M1 - M12) ³⁶
Page Views	4,697
Unique Visitors	1,608
Impressions	62K
Unique Impressions	26.9K
Clicks	1,680
Reactions	2,353
Comments	76
Shares	653
Average Engagement Rate	8.26%
Total Number of Followers	1,071

Figure 42: Cumulated Number of PLATOON Followers - LinkedIn & Twitter (M1 – M11)

³⁶ The PLATOON Consortium decided on a submission date of the D9.3 on 18 December. In the table, the M12 stats have been added on 7 December 2020. Therefore, the complete LinkedIn statistics for M12 will be presented in greater detail in D9.4 (due M26).

Since neither the Twitter, nor the LinkedIn statistics function indicated the cumulated amount of TW³⁷ & LI³⁸ followers btw. M1 and M12, an own graphic has been created to monitor this outcome which can be seen in Fig. 42 above. For this, the number of followers per month (the follower number generated after the corr. month was finished) both for TW & LI have been used to create both graphs. Fig 42 clearly indicates that the months with the largest growth of PLATOON followers were M6 and M7 for both TW and even to a greater extent for LI. Even though in the beginning of the PLATOON project, LI did not grow as fast as TW, from M5 on, the growth in LI followers was much stronger than the growth in followers of TW. Thus, LI surpassed TW in terms of the total number of followers in M6.

3.3. Communication and Dissemination Campaigns

Two campaigns have been created to systematically promote the PLATOON project: the Interviews Campaign (see Chapter 3.3.1) was about the representatives of the PLATOON projects that have been interviewed by the TIB-KTT department during the first project year while the Partners Campaign had a focus on the institutions themselves that act as PLATOON Consortium members.

The current status is that both campaigns have been prepared and should be promoted via SoMe in M12 of this year and during the next project year of PLATOON (M13-M26).

3.3.1 Interviews Campaign

The Interviews Campaign has the purpose to present the PLATOON representatives more in detail in the scope of an interview. Each interviewee has been asked 7 similar questions about his/her role in PLATOON: his/her expectations of the project outcome, as well as the importance of digitalisation of the energy sector and how the future energy sector may look like, according to the interviewee. At the very beginning of the interview, the corr. Interviewee has been briefly presented in a curriculum vitae (CV). Also, a quote pic has been created incl. a photo of the interviewee right next to his/her quote itself. Here, the picture frame for the interviewee image was diamond-like, in order to remind the shape of the PLATOON logo. Each of the tweets/LI posts contains hashtags that indicate important keywords from the interview and the expertise of the corr. interviewee.

As stated at the beginning of Chapter 3.3, the campaign itself will take place in M12 of this year and in the next project year (M13-M26). For this, several tweets and LI posts will be posted on PLATOON's SoMe. Each tweet/LI post will indicate a link to the corr. interview on the website of PLATOON. Further below in Figure 43, the quote pics of the first 12 interviewees are presented.

³⁷ To see the number of TW followers per month, please see Table 2 on page 33 and Table 3 on page 40.

³⁸ To see the number of LI followers per month, please see Table 5 on page 48 and Table 6 on page 52.

Figure 43: PLATOON Interviews Campaign Illustrations and Quotes

3.3.2 Partners Campaign

The Partners Campaign has the aim to present each of the partners of the PLATOON Consortium. For this, the corr. partners should be presented via SoMe. The tweets and LI posts indicate links to the PLATOON website, namely to the blog posts that have been created for each PLATOON company. These blog posts will be published in M12 of this year and in the next project year between M13 and M26. Similarly, as the Interviews Campaign, the tweets and LI posts for the Partners Campaign contain hashtags that match the specific expertise of the corr. company.

Further below in Figure 44, there is a collection of pictures, each indicating both the PLATOON logo and the logo of the corr. PLATOON consortium partner.

Figure 44: PLATOON Partners Campaign Illustrations and Consortium promotion

3.4 Events

3.4.1 Fairs & Online Conferences

During the first year of the H2020 PLATOON project, the PLATOON partners took part in several fairs, both online and physical events, as well as online conferences. The events covered different topics from the energy sector such as energy efficiency in buildings,

innovative technologies in the renewable energy industry, the development of the smart city concept in Europe, among many others. Apart from the energy sector, the PLATOON partners also visited events with a focus on the sustainability/ecology aspect as well as events on the digitalisation of many different tech industries (the energy sector included).

3.4.2 Overview of the PLATOON Fairs & Online Conferences in 2020 (M1-M12)

Below in Table 8, there is a list with all **32 events**³⁹ that the PLATOON partners visited within the time frame M1-M12.

³⁹ Of the 32 events, the TIB-KTT visited **25 events** in total.

Table 8: PLATOON Fairs & Online Conferences in 2020 (M1 - M12)

No.	EVENT	DATE	PLACE	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE	PARTICIPATING PLATOON PARTNERS
1.	Berdeago Energy 2020	31 January - 2 February 2020	Durango, Spain	Berdeago energy 2020 is the annual edition of the energy fair whose program is characterised by different activities and events, with the aim of raising awareness in society and showing the latest developments in products and services in environment, sustainability and energy efficiency.	https://www.berdeago.com/energy/ http://www.clusterenergia.com/event-s/berdeago-energy020-feria-vasca-sostenibilidad-3	GIR
2.	BRIDGE General Assembly in Brussels	11 - 12 February 2020	Brussels, Belgium	BRIDGE is a European Commission initiative which unites Horizon 2020 Smart Grid and Energy Storage Projects to create a structured view of cross-cutting issues which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation.	https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/	ENGIE
3.	Navigating IoT Architectures and Standard Days 2020	19 - 21 February 2020	Brussels, Belgium	NGIoT is a three-year Coordination and Support Action (CSA), started in November 2018. NGIoT consolidates Europe's leading position in creating a secure, safe, trusted and "human-centric" IoT research & innovation, development and deployment environment for The Next Generation Internet (NGI).	https://www.ngiot.eu/event/navigating-iot-architectures-and-standards-days/	ENGIE

4.	1st OPEN DEI Energy Domain Workshop	6 April 2020	Online	OPEN DEI is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the EC under H2020, that aims to detect gaps, encourage synergies, support regional and national cooperation, and enhance communication among the Innovation Actions implementing the EU Digital Transformation strategy. The OPEN DEI project focuses on “Platforms and Pilots” to support the implementation of next generation digital platforms in four basic industrial domains: manufacturing, agriculture, energy and healthcare.	https://www.open-dei.eu/about/#about	CEPV
5.	Berliner Energietage 2020	26 May - 17 June 2020	Online	The Berliner Energietage is the largest conference event and associated trade fair in Germany in the field of energy system transformation. The participants from all over Germany come from politics, associations, public institutions and industry.	https://www.energietage.de/home.html	TIB-KTT
6.	EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020	22 June - 26 June 2020	Online	EU Sustainable Energy Week is an initiative of the European Commission to encourage use of sustainable & renewable energy. Energy Days are digital activities and events organised by local public and private organisations across Europe to promote clean energy and energy efficiency. They are a key component of the EU Sustainable Energy Week.	https://www.eusew.eu/	TIB-KTT

7.	Interreg North-West - Housing 4.0 Energy Supply Chain Workshop	8 July 2020	Online	3 Counties Energy Agency (3CEA) hosted a supply chain workshop which will discuss the Housing 4.0 Energy European project. With the help of industry experts across various sectors, the workshop encouraged participants to come together to share their knowledge and explore the aspects of sustainable energy solutions, building techniques, low carbon construction materials, sustainable manufacturing and supply chain.	https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/h40e-housing-40-energy/events/housing-40-energy-supply-chain-workshop-online/	TIB-KTT
8.	Hannover Messe Digital Days	14 - 15 July 2020	Online	The Hannover Messe Digital Days are a digital conference providing information on trends and innovations in the areas of Industry 4.0, 5G, Artificial Intelligence, Smart Energy and Logistics 4.0.	https://hannovermesse.digital/en/	TIB-KTT
9.	Intersolar Innovation Day	15 - 16 July 2020	Online	With the Innovation Days, the smarter E opens a new digital event series. Exhibitors worldwide present their latest product innovations in interactive live sessions. In addition to the exhibitors' special presentation areas, various surveys, live chats and networking calls offer a variety of opportunities to interact live with the companies and other participants throughout the day.	https://www.themarthere.com/en/events/online-events/intersolar-innovation-day	TIB-KTT
10.	Youth 4 Climate Live Series - Episode 2	24 July	Online	Second Episode "Driving Sustainable Recovery" of the Youth 4 Climate Live Series. It is a youth-focused virtual discussion program building	https://youth4climate.live/	TIB-KTT

				climate ambition in the run-up to 2021's Pre-COP26 in Milan and COP26 in Glasgow.		
11.	Youth 4 Climate Live Series - Episode 3	28 August	Online	This session of the #Youth4ClimateLive Series – “Driving Youth Action” facilitates an intergenerational and interactive virtual conversation between policy makers and unstoppable youth at the forefront of creative climate action. This is the third in a series of monthly events hosted by the Italian Ministry of the Environment in collaboration with Connect4Climate – World Bank Group and the office of the UN Secretary-General’s Envoy on Youth.	https://youth4climate.live/	TIB-KTT
12.	AREA 21 Live Session ⁴⁰ - Developing ICT Tools for District-Scale Smart Energy Management	15 September	Online	AREA 21 (Baltic Smart City Areas for the 21st Century) follows a cooperative approach to develop integrated energy efficiency measures at neighbourhood level. In this context, the project partners are developing so-called EIDs ("Energy Improvement Districts") in various cities in the Baltic Sea Region.	https://area21-project.eu/webinars/ict-solutions/	TIB-KTT
13.	European Research & Innovation Days	22 - 24 September 2020	Online	European Research and Innovation Days is the European Commission’s annual flagship event, bringing together policymakers, researchers, entrepreneurs and citizens to debate and shape the future of research and innovation in Europe and beyond.	https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/events/upcoming-events/european-	TIB-KTT

⁴⁰ The word “webinar” has been replaced by the term “live sessions”.

					research-and-innovation-days_en	
14.	Future Tech Week 2020	21 - 25 September	Online	The Future Tech Week provides EIC Pathfinder FET projects with a unique opportunity and broad platform upon which to showcase their achievements in fields aligning with the European Commission's priorities, including Artificial Intelligence and information technology, health and biotech, culture and society, energy and environment, and nanotech and materials.	http://www.fetfx.eu/event/future-tech-week-2020/	TIB-KTT
15.	ENGIE Innovation Festival 2020	22 - 25 September	Online	This event, entirely devoted to innovation, consists of: a marketplace of innovative solutions around 4 major themes (Carbon Neutrality, Renewable Energies, Cities and Regions, Smart Buildings), along with talks, round tables and masterclasses.	https://engieinnovationfestival.com/	TIB-KTT
16.	OPEN DEI Working Group 3 (WG3) on Linking Ecosystems	23 September	Physical Event	OPEN DEI WG3 is made up of 7 H2020 projects dealing with data exchange and use case applications in the energy field, which have teamed up to facilitate knowledge sharing, exploit dissemination and promote joint activities in the framework of OPEN DEI initiative to make an efficient use of their allocated resources.	http://www.clusterenergia.com/internacional/the-basque-energy-cluster-representing-platoon-project-chairs-open-dei-working-group-3-	CEPV

					wg3-on-linking-ecosystems	
17.	Our Baltic Conference	28 September	Online	Our Baltic gathers ministers, decision makers, scientists and stakeholders from NGOs and industry in the region and across the EU to discuss the challenges faced by the Baltic Sea.	https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/our-baltic-conference_en	TIB-KTT
18.	Solar Power Summit 2020	28 September - 2 October	Online	The SolarPower Summit is SolarPower Europe's annual flagship event, which will bring together over 500 industry representatives from all major energy players, as well as SMEs and a range of decision-makers from across the EU and beyond.	https://www.solarpowersummit.org/	TIB-KTT
19.	NGI Policy Summit 2020	28 - 29 September 2020	online	The NGI Policy Summit is the flagship policy conference of the European Commission's Next Generation Internet (NGI) initiative.	https://www.ngi.eu/event/ngi-policy-summit-2020/	TIB-KTT
20.	INNOVACIÓN EN PRODUCTOS Y SISTEMAS PARA LA CONSTRUCCIÓN (INNOVATION IN PRODUCTS AND SYSTEMS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION)	6 October	Vitoria - Gasteiz, Spain	Presentation of the PLATOON project by Gorka Naveran Lanz, speaker on the topic of Digitisation of facilities and their approach to 4.0 facilities through R&D projects.	https://eventos.infoconstruccion.es/vitoriainnovacionenproductosysistemasparaconstruccion	GIR
21.	FLEXCON 2020	7 - 28 October	Online	FLEXCON is the international event that brings together parties who share the common goal to	https://flexcon2020.eu/flexcon-	TIB-KTT

				engage consumers in the flexible energy revolution. Through our workshops and inclusive talks we relate to new smart energy services and business models, with topics like smart grids, blockchain, energy markets, demand response, transactive energy, smart homes etc.	info/#flexconabout	
22.	IRENA Innovation Week 2020	8 October	Online	Supported by insights from IRENA’s analysis and work on the ground, informed by the experience of recent projects and drawing on the expertise of a diverse range of speakers and attendees, IRENA Innovation Week 2020 will explore the challenges and the emerging innovations in technology, business models and system operation that can support the decarbonisation of the end-use sectors.	https://www.irena.org/events/2020/Oct/IRENA-Innovation-Week-2020	TIB-KTT
23.	MEA Energy Week 2020	19 - 21 October	Online	The Middle East and Africa-focused conference will bring together regional ministers, CEOs, industry leaders and Siemens Energy experts, to discuss the challenges and opportunities facing the energy sector in the evolution and transformation to decarbonised energy systems.	https://www.meaweek.siemens-energy-events.com/signup/landing	TIB-KTT
24.	European Week of Regions and Cities 2020 - Green Europe	19 - 22 October	Online	The European Week of Regions and Cities is the biggest event on EU regional and urban policy, open to all stakeholders. It attracts thousands of practitioners and experts to discuss EU	https://europa.eu/regions-and-cities/home_en	TIB-KTT

				Cohesion Policy. Every year, a number of <u>side events</u> take place around the event.		
25.	FSR Global Energy Innovation Week 2020 Session 1: Digitalisation and long-term investment in energy assets Session 2: Public Financing of green innovation: Matching offers and demand for Financing	26 - 28 October	Online	Energy Innovation Week consists of 3 sessions, which intend to contribute to the identification of common elements of the population of challenges that conform the current regulatory landscape, in order to define a framework that facilitates regulatory learning to realise financing of energy transitions.	https://fsr.eui.eu/event/digitalization-and-long-term-investment-in-energy-assets/	TIB-KTT
26.	Sustainable Places 2020 - Digital Conference	27 - 30 October	Online	Sustainable Places is the only annual international conference focused on showcasing results of EU projects on innovation for the built environment. The 8th edition, Sustainable Places 2020 (27-30 October 2020), has been held over four days in virtual format to facilitate thematic presentations and fruitful discussion on topics such as circular economy, digital twins, BIPV, local energy communities, sustainable digital infrastructure, etc.	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/home/sp2020-agenda/	ENGIE

27.	European Big Data Value Forum	3 - 5 November	Online	EBDVF 2020 aims to continue the success of the previous editions, which were attended on average by 600 participants and especially industry professionals, business developers, researchers, and policymakers coming from over 40 countries.	https://www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/about-ebdvf/	ENGIE, TIB-KTT, ENG, TIB
28.	GAIA-X Summit	18 - 19 November	Online	With GAIA-X, representatives from politics, business and science from France and Germany, together with other European partners, create a proposal for the next generation of a data infrastructure for Europe: a secure, federated system that meets the highest standards of digital sovereignty while promoting innovation.	https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html	TIB-KTT
29.	DN Unlimited 2020	18 - 20 November	Online	Data Natives Unlimited is a series of online and offline events that aims to bring data and tech professionals, established companies, public institutions and governments together to share knowledge, co-create solutions, establish relationships and celebrate the achievements of data scientists, founders, entrepreneurs and activists.	https://datanatives.io/	TIB-KTT
30.	WindTV at WindEnergy Hamburg	1 - 4 December	Online	The world's leading wind energy event brings together the most important representatives from politics, industry and research in a global, digital meeting. A highlight will be the Premium Conference of WindEurope, which will take place as planned, but also digitally. For the first	https://www.windenergyhamburg.com/en/event/windtv/programme/	TIB-KTT

				time there will be a 'Wind TV Channel' in parallel to the actual conference programme, giving participants access to exclusive live and on-demand content.		
31.	Data Sharing Winter School (IDSA event)	2 - 4 December	Online	12 sessions will be discussing major topics of research in the field of data sharing. Hosted by prominent experts, these meetings will present state-of-the-art approaches using concrete examples taken from the manufacturing sector. One session will be specifically focused on up and running implementations of data spaces and their presentation.	https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/data-sharing-winter-school/	TIB-KTT
32.	EuroPCom 2020 - Time for Communication	7 - 8 December	Online	EuroPCom 2020 - Time for Communication is fully online and will look at the opportunities and challenges in communication around three key themes: Citizens, Green and Digital.	https://cor.europa.eu/en/events/Pages/europcom.aspx	TIB-KTT

Figure 45: SISTEPLANT, TECNALIA and Giroa-Véolia at Nanogune Pilot (Part 1)

Figure 46: SISTEPLANT, TECNALIA and Giroa-Véolia at Nanogune Pilot (Part 2)

Figure 47: SISTEPLANT, TECNALIA and Giroa-Véolia at Nanogune Pilot (Part 3)

On 22 July, there was a meeting between SISTEPLANT, TECNALIA, and Giroa-Véolia (Fig. 45 - 47) in order to visit Nanogune's pilot in Spain and get more familiar with the facilities.

3.4.3 EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020

Figure 48: Logo of the EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020

The **EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020 (EUSEW2020)**⁴¹ is the biggest event dedicated to renewables and efficient energy use in Europe. It is made up of a 3-day policy conference offering various networking opportunities, an EU Sustainable Energy Awards competition with a public vote for the Citizens' Award and local

events held across Europe throughout the months of May and June. The EUSEW2020 took place from 22 to 26 June 2020 under the theme: **'Beyond the crisis: clean energy for green recovery and growth'**. The main topics were the EU Green Deal, the Green Recovery plan after the COVID-19 crisis, the Renovation Wave of buildings within the EU, the role of renewable energy sources and green hydrogen in the energy sector of the future, innovative energy efficiency measures, smart cities and the importance of flexibility in the energy industry, among others. European and non-European stakeholders from the energy industry and beyond took part in the EUSEW2020 events. Among the online event speakers were high-ranking persons from the energy industry, such as **EU Commissioner for Energy Kadri Simson, Executive VP for the EU Green Deal and First VP of the EC Frans Timmermans, Director General of the EC Ditte Juul Jorgensen, Executive Director of IEA Fatih Birol**, among others.

Figure 49: EUSEW2020 Preview Picture

Alexandra Garatzogianni, Communication & Dissemination WP9 Lead, and Michael Fribus, Communication & Dissemination WP9 Deputy both took part in the 'EU Youth Energy Day 2020' event and the EUSEW2020 'Policy Conference' events and represented TIB and the PLATOON project. During the 'Policy Conference', which took place from 23 to 25 June 2020, **Alexandra Garatzogianni and Michael Fribus visited 11 online events**. These were:

⁴¹ The Twitter account of EUSEW2020 (@euenergyweek) can be accessed here: <https://twitter.com/euenergyweek>

- Debate with Ambassadors
- Energy transition towards climate neutrality: the EU's support for clean energy technologies and innovation
- EU Green Deal & the ways out of the COVID-19 crisis: a high-level debate about the greening of the EU recovery
- The role of local authorities in a fair energy transition, through retrofitting buildings
- Clean.Competitive.Connected: how to successfully design smart sector integration in the twin climate & digital transition
- Energy system integration - powering a climate neutral economy
- Unlocking Investment through climate advisory by the European Investment Advisory Hub
- New instruments to support a Green Recovery in Europe - the modernisation and innovation funds
- Smart grids and flexibility markets: status of demonstrators and effect of COVID-19 on the demo operation and results
- European Green Deal – NECPs at your service
- Boosting the hydrogen economy through international cooperation

The participation in the EUSEW2020 online events as well as the networking with other participants contributed to a rapid increase of Followers both on LinkedIn (+ **200 New Followers**) and Twitter (+ **100 New Followers**) in June 2020. For Twitter this can be seen in Fig. 16 on p. 32 & Fig. 17 on p. 34; for LinkedIn, this can be seen best in Fig. 34 on p. 47 and in Fig. 50 on page 70. Therefore, the EUSEW2020 has turned out to be a big success for the **Knowledge and Tech Transfer Department of TIB (TIB-KTT)**, PLATOON’s WP9 and the project.

The Twitter account of EUSEW2020 (@euenergyweek) can be accessed here: <https://twitter.com/euenergyweek>

Figure 50: Impact of the EUSEW2020 on the Amount of New PLATOON LinkedIn Followers

Figure 51: EUSEW2020 Tweets on PLATOON Twitter Account

Figure 52: EUSEW2020 Posts on PLATOON LinkedIn Account

3.4.4 SolarPower Summit 2020

The SolarPower Summit is SolarPower Europe’s annual flagship event and one of the biggest solar power events in Europe. It brings together over 500 industry representatives from all major energy players, as well as SMEs and a range of decision-makers from across the EU and beyond. The key highlights of the SolarPower Summit 2020 were:

Figure 53: SolarPower Summit 2020 Preview Picture

- 2000+ registered attendees
- 60 confirmed speakers
- 70+ pre-scheduled B2B matchmaking meetings
- 26 partners and supporters
- 14 sponsors
- 160,000+ impressions on Twitter
- 17,600+ impressions on LinkedIn

3.5 Open Calls (FBA)

The project dissemination activities will be further supported by the open calls dissemination activities that include:

- A preparation stage of activities,
- The launch of the open calls,
- The communication activities to attract applicants and;
- A final press release and infographic illustrating the main results of the open call.

The preparation stage involves the development of a communication toolkit that will be sent to the partners so that they can also promote the open call. This also includes the promotional pieces for other relevant channels that are going to be used to communicate about the open call. The open Call will be announced on the PLATOON website, with a direct link to the Open Call micro-site with further details about the Call as well as access to the application form deployed by FundingBox.

There will also be a press release that will be sent to different media outlets, and partners will be asked to send it to their local media. Online paid ad campaigns will also be used to target specific regions or groups in order to encourage and secure an important number of applications.

Once the open call is launched on the 4th of January 2021, there will be regular posting on different social media channels, and promotion via the PLATOON newsletter. Partners should also post on their social media accounts and make reference in their newsletter. For these, they will have a communication toolkit that will be provided by FundingBox.

The PLATOON consortium partners and particularly TIB and CEPV will also commit to several Face-to-face actions including:

(1) **Info days** to inform potential FSTP recipients in prioritised verticals about an upcoming open call

(2) **Info corners in world-class events at EU Level.** We will attend EU world-class events, within the prioritised verticals, specifically addressed to disseminate an open call. (3). Live Sessions (virtual info sessions).

We, with the support of FBA, will also organise 2 web-based info sessions to disseminate an open call. The agenda will include a brief presentation of the project, the open call requirements and a slot for proposers' time, where potential applicants can present their project ideas and look for potential partners. The sessions will be recorded for participants to be able to play the web-stream video recording at any time.

Once an open call closes, a press release with an infographic informing the results of the number of applications will be published and sent to media outlets as well.

3.6 Ambassadors (FBA)

The objective of the NGI Ambassadors Programme is to increase the community of PLATOON, raise its awareness and visibility and enhance the connections of its members.

NGI ambassadors are renowned and recognised experts in Research, Political, Activism and Business sectors, with a push of followers and proven influence on big data and the energy domain.

There will be **3 types of ambassadors**:

1. **Influencers:** well-known people from big data and the energy domain that have a massive network of followers and would be able to attract users to our community.
2. **Experts / Interlocutors:** not so well-known people but interesting providers of content to our community.
3. **Early adopters:** including beneficiaries from our open calls, or external parties, namely

SMEs and start-ups that can showcase how they are applying these technologies in real life or business.

The selected PLATOON ambassadors are enlisted to

1. Disseminate information through their networks on the PLATOON project.
2. Create brand awareness around a specific topic or area related to big data and energy, so their recognition contributes to generate brand awareness around PLATOON.
3. Provide content from their experience, work, and networks, all related to PLATOON, on a regular basis and stay tuned to our social media and share some posts and tweets.
4. Contribute to 1 or 2 Q&A or web-based info sessions.

The Ambassadors' Programme intends to sign up at least 4 influencers along the length of the project.

3.7 Supportive Partners Programme (FBA)

The Supportive Partners Programme for communities will involve entities from across Europe, such as start-up communities, accelerators, governments, programmes and more to help PLATOON to empower innovation and entrepreneurship in the crossroads of ICT and energy and connect the ecosystem. The “supportive partners” are stakeholders interested in disseminating the project in a win-win cooperation mode. These are identified via community mapping, starting from the PLATOON partners' networks. PLATOON's target is to identify **20 supportive partners**.

For this purpose, each partner was asked by FBA to identify these entities within their network. The reason for triggering this process initially among the core partners of the project is to benefit from the direct knowledge of such entities during already established business relations or previous cooperation in other projects.

An email template was provided for the partners' to send to their respective contacts that could act as supportive partners. This email highlighted the value proposition for collaboration namely asking the aforementioned entities to act as multipliers, helping PLATOON increase the outreach of the Open Call process and to ensure applicants come from beyond our immediate networks. In return, PLATOON committed to offer them:

1. Visibility on FBA's online community, the PLATOON website, newsletter and social media channels.
2. A chance to showcase success stories and share content of their own activity through PLATOON's communication links.
3. A possibility to include to join as mentors/evaluators, or to nominate companies in their portfolios, where relevant.
4. Networking opportunities and a chance to reach collaboration agreements for joint presence at events and to co-organise info sessions

So far, FBA together with the PLATOON partners have identified and reached out to 15 supportive partners.

5. Following a response from the supportive partners expressing interest in the role, FBA reached out to each to on-board the confirmed supportive partners. To date, FBA has contacted 15 supportive partners, as a result of the outreach activity run by several of PLATOON partners.

Entities willing to join and collaborate with the project will be asked to express their commitment, which will include at least:

- Name of the organisation, logo, site and social media.
- Contact for communication (name and mail).
- Permission to receive information from PLATOON.
- Interest in sharing information with the PLATOON ecosystem and corresponding permission.
- Accepting the terms of PLATOON's Privacy Policy.

Interest and commitment of entities on collaborating with PLATOON will be maintained by periodic communication. This interaction will be based on a communication package with the support of the partners and consisting of suggested banners, social media posts and stories to share with their networks online, in printed media and via their newsletters.

In addition, some collaborating entities will be encouraged to share content for dissemination so that the community as a whole would benefit from channelling all information into one place. Content can include, for example:

- Success stories about the implementation of the pilot.
- Recent breakthrough and advances benefiting and business news in this domain,
- Opportunities for SMEs: calls, events, competitions, etc.

Action Plan*Table 9: Action Plan for PLATOON Open Call Communication and Dissemination Activities*

ACTION	DESCRIPTION
Communication Toolkit	<p>Communication toolkit for PLATOON project partners will be created to disseminate the open call that will be launched on 4th January 2021 (M13). This toolkit will also be shared with the Supportive Partners and Ambassadors to do cross-dissemination.</p> <p>The communication toolkit should include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PR about the Open Call. 2. Content and Banners about the Open Call. 3. Social media posts examples for Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. 4. Email templates. <p>The content and call to action is focused on applying for the open call. All partners should distribute it within their networks trying to reach out to the media and other entities interested in cross-dissemination or in collaborating with the PLATOON project.</p>
Branded Content/Banners in specialised media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A list of specialised media about the Open Call will be created. • FBA and TIB will reach out to media platforms (newspapers, magazines, blogs) with the PR and banners to see if they publish it for free or negotiate a sponsored article. • FBA will also share posts in the relevant communities on their Online Community Platform: Funding Opportunities on FundingBox Community⁴².
Newsletter & Email Campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the open call will be included in the PLATOON newsletter and all partners should also include a section about the Open Call in their newsletters. • The email template included in the communication toolkit with the call to action ‘Apply for PLATOON open call’ will be sent to all partners’ databases.

⁴² <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/c/fundingbox-community/collections/showcase>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners should also send it to possible collaborators (influencers and other supportive entities) under cross-dissemination purposes.
Search Engine Marketing	An online marketing campaign will be launched, including AdWords (Search and Display), optimised by a marketing agency or freelancer.
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Owned social media: Regularly posts on social media about the Open Call via PLATOON’s social media accounts. Shared social media: All partners should share on their social media accounts posts about the PLATOON Open Call with help from the communication toolkit.
Offline Events	<p>PLATOON will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use targeted events to promote face-to-face PLATOON open calls by distributing flyers/one-pager. Gather leads and send them personalised follow up emails about PLATOON Open Call. Organise 6 info days, at national level, organised by core technical partners before both of the Open Calls. Organise Info corners: attendance to main related events at the European level to inform about the Open Calls.
Live Sessions & Q&A Sessions	PLATOON will organise at least two info or Q&A sessions about a PLATOON Open Call in the PLATOON community in order to support the application process for participants.
Reminders Emails	<p>Reminders will be sent to applicants who have begun an application form with the call to action ‘Submit your application’:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> One month to the deadline. Two weeks to the deadline. One week to the deadline. Three days to the deadline. One day to the deadline. Submission day.
Surveys	Once the open call deadline has passed, a survey about the Open Call could be sent to applicants in order to get feedback and improve the process.
PR after the open call	A press release will be launched after the Open Call deadline, listing the main results in terms of received applications and the next steps that will follow. There will also be an infographic illustrating these results.

3.8 Scientific Dissemination (TIB-SDM)

The technologies developed in the context of the PLATOON project have been disseminated in various venues, where the partners of the consortium have actively participated during the period M7-M12. This section reports on the scientific events and publications of the project. These events are divided in a) Scientific Publications and b) Presentations in conferences, forums, workshops, and panels.

3.8.1 Scientific Publications

The scientific contributions of PLATOON have been reported in scientific events and . one scientific article was already published by the M12 (i.e. deadline of submission of this deliverable). This is a publication in the proceedings of an international conference which is peer-reviewed following a single-blind modality, and at least two reviewers have evaluated each publication; they are openly accessible. Table 10 describes this publications and provides an open access link.

Table 10 Scientific Publications

PUBLICATION TYPE	TITLE & LINK	AUTHORS	VENUE	YEAR
Proceedings in International Conference	Electricity Balancing: Challenges and Perspectives 10.1109/TELFOR51502.2020.9306549	Valentina Janev, Goran Jakupović	Proc. of the 28th IEEE Telecommunications Forum https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/9306507/proceeding	2020

3.8.2 Presentation in International Conferences, Forums, and Workshops

In addition to the events represented in section 3.4.2, the consortium partners have participated in one international scientific event during the reporting period. The events include presentations in international conferences or workshops, invited talks in summer schools and forums, and participation on panels (Table 11). These events enabled the discussion of scientific and technological challenges of data management, knowledge representation, and artificial intelligence in data spaces.

Table 11 Participation in Scientific Events

TYPE	EVENT NAME	PARTNER	DATE
International Forum	Focus Track 1: European Data Spaces- Main session at European Big Data Value 2020 https://2020.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/agenda/	TIB	3 November 2020

3.9 Industrial Dissemination (CEPV)

According to the PLATOON Dissemination and Communication Strategy defined in the deliverable D9.1, the main target audiences for the project results are related to the different industrial company profiles operating in the energy sector. In particular, the industrial dissemination activities planned and to be carried out in the scope of Task 9.3 are specifically addressed to the following target segments of the energy value chains:

- Developers and/or owners of energy assets,
- O&M service providers,
- Wind turbine Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs, Tier 1),
- Equipment and components manufacturers (Tier 2 and 3),
- ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) companies,
- Research and development centres - testing facilities.

In order to reach relevant companies from these target segments, PLATOON partners have carried out a number of dissemination activities during the first project year, which are reported in the following subsections.

It needs to be mentioned that the industrial dissemination and communication activities, as they were initially planned, have been in several ways affected by the COVID-19 measures each country has taken, especially with regard to the organisation of events, exhibitions and conferences where the project concept, objectives and preliminary outcomes could have been disseminated.

Nevertheless, since the project was still at a very early stage when the pandemic struck, the industrial dissemination team has been able to initiate some mitigation measures addressed to replace the face-to-face activities that could not be carried out in the first year by other equivalent ones enabling stakeholder interaction through virtual channels and tools. This way, the team is quite confident to keep the industrial dissemination going on at an acceptable pace in the following months and progressively recover the face-to-face interaction when the emergency measures are no longer necessary.

3.9.1 Participation in relevant exhibitions, events and conferences of the energy sector

Exhibitions, conferences and large face-to-face events in general have suffered the greatest impact from the COVID-19 measures. Along this year, PLATOON had planned to be showcased in at least 4 major conferences and exhibitions closely related to the energy sector: **Hannover Messe** (April 2020), **Intersolar/EES Munich** (June 2020), **WindEnergy Hamburg** (September 2020) and **Enlit (European Utility Week + Powergen)** Milan (October 2020). All of them have been cancelled and postponed to 2021.

Since the greatest advantage of these major events is their ability to bring together entities of heterogeneous profiles, thus covering the entire value chain in their respective target segments, the project participation is still regarded as key when they finally take place in order to reach the project's target audience segments. Therefore, dissemination of the project progress through talks, posters and prints in the attending partners' booths at these events is still foreseen in 2021.

Participation in WindEnergy Hamburg Digital Event (December 1st-4th 2020)

In spite of the challenging situation related to face-to-face events and exhibitions, PLATOON had the chance to be showcased in the WindEnergy Hamburg event (<https://www.windenergyhamburg.com/>), which was for the first time held as a purely virtual event through a powerful digital platform with a comprehensive programme from 1 to 4 December 2020. The platform and its related contents, aimed to interconnect the players of the wind industry on their only global marketplace this year, will remain online all the way up to the next WindEnergy Hamburg in September 2022.

PLATOON participation at the event was focused on two main activities:

- Overall project presentation by Jose I. Hormaeche (CEPV) on behalf of the PLATOON consortium at the "Speakers' Corner" on Dec. 4th. (<https://www.windenergyhamburg.com/en/news-topics/highlights/speakers-corner/>).

Figure 54: PLATOON presentation at the Speakers' Corner
(WindEnergy Hamburg Digital Event 2020)

- Project showcase at the event’s digital platform: a description of the project together with the logo and the digital version of the project poster have been uploaded to the online platform and will be available until September 2022.

Figure 55: PLATOON poster displayed at the WindEnergy Hamburg digital platform

3.9.2 Periodic contacts and launch of collaboration initiatives with selected entities and stakeholders

Regarding collaborative initiatives with key groups and stakeholders for the PLATOON industrial dissemination objectives, the OPEN DEI initiative has been identified as a very relevant forum to facilitate interaction, mutual knowledge and exchange of best practices and

results between a number of projects specifically focused in providing added value to energy stakeholders through efficient data handling, processing and analysis.

[OPEN DEI⁴³](#) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the EC under H2020, that aims to detect gaps, encourage synergies, support regional and national cooperation, and enhances communication among the Innovation Actions implementing the EU Digital Transformation strategy. The OPEN DEI project focuses on “Platforms and Pilots” to support the implementation of next generation digital platforms in four basic industrial domains: Manufacturing, agriculture, energy and healthcare.

The Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) - as Industrial Dissemination task leader - has taken care of the representation of the project and its participation in the OPEN DEI initiative, keeping close contact with its promoters throughout the year, even before the industrial dissemination task officially started.

Considering the global COVID-19 situation and the limitations posed by the lockdowns in the different countries, the project engagement with the OPEN DEI initiative and its related activities has turned out to be a very efficient way to meet and collaborate with other energy stakeholders sharing common needs, expectations and technological capabilities to deliver digital solutions. This collaboration will be strengthened over the coming years through jointly developed activities and is expected to provide a valuable input to achieve the project objectives.

Further details on the activities carried out this year in the framework of the OPEN DEI initiative are provided here below.

Participation in OPEN DEI energy workshop (April 6th, 2020)

As a first step, PLATOON participated in the 1st OPEN DEI energy domain virtual workshop, which was held on April 6th, 2020. Jose I. Hormaeche (CEPV), on behalf of the PLATOON consortium, explained the main goals and the developments planned and introduced the large-scale pilots foreseen in the project.

Representatives from DG ENER, DG CONNECT and seven H2020 projects (being PLATOON one of them) took part in the workshop, exchanged information about their projects and explored synergies and areas of common interest in order to set up specific working groups.

This workshop made it possible to establish links among the participating H2020 projects in the energy ecosystem – all of them dealing with data exchange and use case applications - and to set up working groups and joint actions for the upcoming period.

⁴³ Cf. <https://www.opendei.eu/about/#about>

Figure 56: Diss of PLATOON participation in the 1st OPEN DEI energy workshop (CEPV)

Figure 57: CEPV post on the PLATOON participation in the 1st OPEN DEI energy workshop

The workshop and the participation of PLATOON was disseminated on CEPV website (<http://www.clusterenergia.com/cluster-activities/platoon-participates-in-open-dei-energy-workshop-3>) and CEPV social networks (LI: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6652898131597901824>).

Coordination and kick-off meeting of OPEN DEI working group 3 (WG3) on Linking ecosystems (September 23th, 2020)

Because of the participation of PLATOON in the 1st OPEN DEI energy workshop, the Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) volunteered on behalf of the consortium to coordinate one of the working groups (WG) identified: WG3, dealing with Linking ecosystems.

WG3 is made up of the seven H2020 projects participating in OPEN DEI initiative, which have specifically teamed up to facilitate knowledge sharing, exploit dissemination and promote joint activities in the framework of OPEN DEI in order to make an efficient use of their allocated resources.

WG3 was officially launched in an online kick-off meeting held on September 23rd, 2020. José I. Hormaeche (CEPV) - WG3 leader on behalf of PLATOON project - presented the main WG goals and a preliminary action plan for 2020 and 2021 including, among other activities, mutual exchange of information about the participating projects, dissemination of the open calls to be launched by the projects and organisation of joint dissemination events.

The meeting was co-chaired by Alberto Dognini (OPEN DEI) and attended by representatives from BD4OPEM, INTERFACE and INTERCONNECT projects. In addition, representatives from DGCONNECT and ENTSOE provided valuable insights for the WG development.

The WG3 launch and kick-off meeting was disseminated on CEPV website (<http://www.clusterenergia.com/cluster-activities/the-basque-energy-cluster-representing-platoon-project-chairs-open-dei-working-group-3-wg3-on-linking-ecosystems-3>) and CEPV social networks (TT: https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/status/1315933734374342663; LI: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6721702966329450496>). Monthly conference calls will be held to check progress on WG activities and coordinate specific actions.

Figure 58: Dissemination of OPEN DEI WG3 launch and kick-off meeting chaired by PLATOON (CEPV)

Figure 59: CEPV tweet on the OPEN DEI WG3 launch and kick-off meeting chaired by PLATOON

Follow-up meeting of OPEN DEI working group 3 (WG3) on Linking ecosystems (October 30th, 2020)

The meeting was chaired by José I. Hormaeche (CEPV) on behalf of the PLATOON project and attended by representatives from INTERRFACE and INTERCONNECT projects as well as from the OPENDEI management team.

During the meeting, short presentations from the attending projects were shared, outlining their main objectives, partners and planned schedule, expected results and pilots, and target markets/audiences. In addition, preliminary information about the Open calls for cascade funding to be launched by the projects in the following months was exchanged, looking for a better synchronisation among the different projects' topics and schedule for such Open calls.

Finally, a preliminary proposal for a joint dissemination event to be held in the 1st quarter of 2021 was discussed and agreed to be developed in subsequent meetings.

Follow-up meeting of OPEN DEI working group 3 (WG3) on Linking ecosystems (November 27th, 2020)

The meeting was chaired by José I. Hormaeche (CEPV) on behalf of the PLATOON project and attended by representatives from BD4OPEM, INTERRFACE and INTERCONNECT projects. In addition, representatives from DGCONNECT and ENTSOE provided valuable input and comments for the WG development.

The topics dealt with in this meeting were the following:

- Organisation of periodic contributions from each project to the Newsletter of OPEN DEI.
- Use of the OPEN DEI repository and website to include dissemination material and links to the different projects' websites.

- Confirmation of dates, formats, participants and agenda for the joint dissemination event to be organised in 2021. Agreement on tasks and deadlines.
- Schedule of meetings and contents for 2021

Organisation of an event hosted by PLATOON in the framework of OPEN DEI

As mentioned in the previous OPEN DEI WG3 activity report, a joint dissemination event to be held in the 1st quarter of 2021 was identified as one of the target activities to be developed in the framework of the WG3 activity. Details for this event are further elaborated in the following subsection.

3.9.3 Organisation of workshops and conferences, targeted to industrial European audiences

As a result, from the meetings held in the framework of the OPEN DEI WG3, an event hosted by PLATOON and co-located to the PLATOON General Assembly in February 2021 (4th and 5th) is currently under preparation. The event focused on “Data sharing and governance for Energy applications”, will be held in Bilbao on February 3rd (the day before the PLATOON General Assembly) in a mixed face-to-face and online format (via streaming).

The tentative agenda is structured in three main blocks:

- Institutional opening, with representatives from the Basque Country Government and the European Commission.
- Panel on Data governance, with keynote speeches from TECN (PLATOON Technical Coordinator), OPEN DEI and IDSA (International Data Space), among others.
- Panel on projects and pilots in energy data sharing, including pitch presentations of the projects that participate in the OPEN DEI Energy domain Working Group, a round table with representatives from those projects, chaired by OPEN DEI and a final wrap-up conducted by ENGIE (PLATOON project Coordinator).

The project team will be actively involved in the organisation of this event during the first weeks of 2021.

3.9.4 Workshops and meetings with stakeholders at national and regional level

One of the main target segments of the industrial dissemination activities are component manufacturers: thanks to the platforms and tools to be developed in the project, these companies will have access to data provided by Data owners, allowing them to analyse those data in order to improve their designs and extend their products’ lifecycle.

In this sense, the Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) – as Industrial dissemination task leader – has launched a dissemination campaign specifically targeted to this segment that will be further developed throughout the project covering different profiles of component manufacturers in the energy value chains.

Presentation of PLATOON project in a workshop with wind energy companies (September 25th, 2020)

The Basque Energy Cluster organised a workshop with a group of 22 industrial stakeholders from the wind energy field in San Sebastian, in which the PLATOON project was presented.

The workshop was set as a kick-off event of a new Working Group (WG) promoted by the Cluster and focused on Wind turbine data sharing, which intends to provide wind turbine component manufacturers with access to the data required to operate wind farms, so that they can obtain value from them and improve their competitiveness. Wind turbine component manufacturers, software companies and agents from the Basque Science, Technology and Innovation Network have joined and will actively participate in the group.

José I. Hormaeche (CEPV), explained the PLATOON concept, objectives and expected outcomes to the attendees, who participated both in person and online. The project scope is closely linked to the WG objectives and expectations, especially regarding the use and analysis of the available data for improved efficiency, operation and maintenance purposes, which is a key issue for the companies attending the meeting.

Since the WG will hold follow-up meetings and workshops on a regular basis, these will represent a good opportunity to update the wind energy industrial stakeholders on the project progress and outcomes, as well as to collect useful feedback regarding market needs and expectations.

The workshop was disseminated on CEPV website (<http://www.clusterenergia.com/international/the-basque-energy-cluster-presents-platoon-project-to-wind-energy-companies-3>) and on CEPV social networks (TW: https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/status/1316308846290313221; LI: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6722076292864385024>).

Figure 60: Dissemination of CEPV workshop with wind energy industrial stakeholders

Figure 61: Tweet on CEPV workshop with wind energy industrial stakeholders

Dissemination of PLATOON in the European Cluster Conference (November 10th- 11th, 2020)

The first fully virtual European Cluster Conference (<https://www.eucluster2020.eu/ecc2020>) was organised on 10 and 11 November 2020 by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs together with the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy under the German Presidency of the Council of the EU.

The conference - executed by the European Cluster Collaboration Platform – brought together 1000 stakeholders, policymakers, cluster managers, researchers, entrepreneurs and the public to discuss and share current and future priorities for cluster policies and developments to support sustainable industry development and interregional cooperation, and to build connections between Europe’s value chains, clusters and ecosystems.

Figure 62: CEPV presentation at the Renewable energy breakout session (European Cluster Conference 2020)

José I. Hormaeche (CEPV) participated in the breakout sessions on November 11th, focused on clusters strengthening industrial ecosystems. In particular, he took part as a speaker in a session focused on Renewable energy, where he had the opportunity to disseminate PLATOON project activity, among other topics in his presentation.

Presentation of PLATOON project in a technology workshop on digitalisation in the energy value chains (November 24th, 2020)

The Basque Energy Cluster organised a technology workshop with a group of 52 industrial stakeholders and knowledge agents from different energy value chains in Zamudio, in which the PLATOON project was presented. The event gathered 96 people combining 19 face-to-face participants (considering covid-19 room limitations) and 77 online attendees.

The objective of the workshop was twofold: on the one hand, to disseminate the competences and capabilities from Basque knowledge agents on digital technologies (data sharing, data platforms, lake houses, edge computing, etc.) related to the acquisition and exploitation of data from assets and power plants in operation and, on the other hand, to show success stories of companies that already embedded such technologies into their products and/or services, which might be an inspiring reference for other companies in the Basque industrial ecosystem.

José I. Hormaeche (CEPV), made an overall presentation of the PLATOON project and announced the launch of the first PLATOON Open Call on January 4th, encouraging the companies to stay tuned for further details to come in the following weeks.

Figure 63: Technology workshop on digitalisation in the energy sector - auditorium view

The workshop was disseminated on CEPV social networks (TT: https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/status/1331180235887349762?s=20).

Figure 64: Dissemination of CEPV technology workshop on digitalisation of the energy sector

3.10 Communication & Dissemination KPIs for 2020 (M1-M12)

Table 12: Comm & Diss KPIs for 2020 (M1-M12) - Reference Values & Actual Values

KPIs	REFERENCE VALUES	ACTUAL VALUES (M12 ⁴⁴)
Leaflets, Posters	> 10 national/ international events	18
Press Releases	> 8 by end of the project	2
Social Media	1,000 Followers on Twitter by end of the project	> 600 Followers on Twitter

⁴⁴ Status: 07.12.2020.

	15,000 impressions	> 1000 Followers on LinkedIn > 30,000 per month
Meetings & Workshops	> 20 events	> 32

Figure 65: Highlights – PLATOON KPIs in 2020 (M1-M12)

To conclude Chapter 3, the highlights of the WP9 KPIs achieved in the first year of the project are briefly described below. Further above, Table 10 shows the KPIs that were set at the beginning of the PLATOON project and the actual values achieved while Figure 65 shows the highlights of the PLATOON comm & diss achievements.

Within less than a year, the PLATOON **Twitter** account could acquire **over 600 followers**, while the PLATOON **LinkedIn** account gained **over 1000 followers**. Compared to similar H2020 energy project accounts that have existed longer than PLATON but often could generate a smaller number of followers, these are outstanding results. Moreover, **2 PLATOON press releases** on the kick-off of the PLATOON project as well as the launch of the PLATOON Community respectively, have been published during the first project year. Also, **6 different** kinds of **PLATOON printed materials** - 2 stickers, 2 brochures both in A1 and A4 format, 1 flyer and 1 banner, have been developed in the first quarter of 2020. During the first year of the

project a total of **32 events** were visited, both online and offline, of which **25** were visited by the **TIB-KTT** department. All events were either energy- or digitalisation-related, or covered aspects that were compatible with PLATOON such as sustainability, climate action, and innovative technologies, among others.

All in all, from a communication & dissemination point of view, the first PLATOON project year (M1-M12) proved to be very fruitful for T9.1 & T9.4 of WP9. **Thus, Task 9.1 and Task 9.4 of the WP9 were ahead of schedule and successful in 2020.**

4. Collaboration with BDVA

The PLATOON further developed the close collaboration with BDVA. Various PLATOON Consortium partners (ENGIE, PUPIN, VUB etc.) join BDVA as full and associate members. The PLATOON project was a sponsor for the European Big Data Value Forum⁴⁵ (EBDVF) 2020. During the EBDVF Conference, the Coordinator of PLATOON presented the project and the communication team (TIB-KTT) actively promoted the project and the event. Various synergies are planned with the BDVA community and are currently in progress. The outcomes of the ongoing discussions will be reported in the upcoming versions of this deliverable.

Figure 66: Promotion the of EBDVF2020 event on PLATOON Twitter Account

⁴⁵ Cf. <https://www.bdva.eu/node/1440>

Figure 67: Promotion of the EBDVF2020 event on PLATOON LinkedIn Account

5. BRIDGE

Close collaboration is further maintained with BRIDGE, the European Commission initiative which unites Horizon 2020 Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation Projects to create a structured view of cross-cutting issues which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation. The Coordinator of PLATOON has regularly presented the project to the BRIDGE community. The communication team (TIN-KTT) regularly implement promotion actions and collaborate with the comm lead of BRIDGE.

Figure 68: Promotion of the BRIDGE Brochure on PLATOON Twitter Account

Figure 69: Promotion of BRIDGE Brochure on PLATOON LinkedIn Account

Latest status:

PLATOON and TIB promoted the BRIDGE brochure via the PLATOON Twitter and LinkedIn channels. Moreover, a blog post about the BRIDGE brochure has been edited on the PLATOON website and was also promoted via PLATOON’s social media channels.

6. Assessing the Impact of the COVID-19 Outbreak

The PLATOON Consortium is updated as per all the measures of the EC with relation to the ongoing EU-funded projects and this topic is discussed regularly at the level of the Steering Committee, aiming to mitigate potential negative impacts for the project. Nevertheless, it is a fact that during the first year of the project, conferences in which the PLATOON project would have been presented are being postponed for 2021. Such examples are the Hannover Messe 2020, which was initially postponed to July 2020 and then to April 2021 and the BDVA Summit in Porto. TIB, as WPL9, will facilitate this process by offering online alternatives, e.g. by proposing to the partners the organisation of live sessions in which they can present the PLATOON project.

To counteract the COVID implications, the TIB-KTT team has been intensively active via social media and during online events and conferences, succeeding thus in implementing impactful outreach and project promotion across related and relevant stakeholders.

7. Conclusion & Future Outlook

From a communication & dissemination point of view, the first project year (M1-M12) was a great success for the WP9 and the PLATOON project.

The PLATOON project acquired a great number of followers both on LinkedIn and Twitter and was able to build a community with stakeholders from the energy sector and beyond. As a reaction to the COVID-19 outbreak and its resulting consequences, the WP9 Lead and WP9 Deputy worked increasingly online, thus used alternative opportunities such as online events, online campaigns, online workshops among many other tools to disseminate the PLATOON project activities. Therefore, the online activities were key for the generation of new followers and growth of the PLATOON community.

Overall, despite the COVID 19 pandemic and the resulting situation, the TIB-KTT Division can report a very large success for WP9, Tasks 9.1 and 9.4 in 2020. The PLATOON partners are striving for this success also in the second project year (M13-M26). In 2021, the PLATOON Community is expected to further grow, and the PLATOON open calls, live sessions, workshops, and new marketing campaigns will raise awareness for the digitalisation of the European energy sector to an even greater extent.

8. Internal Review

8.1 Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Philippe Calvez

Organisation: ENGIE

Date: 20/12/2020

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?					
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?					
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?					
... contain a version table?					
... contain an updated table of contents?					
... contain a list of figures?					
... contain a list of tables?					
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?					

... contain an Executive Summary?					
... contain a Conclusions section?					
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?					
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?					
... use correct spelling and grammar?					
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)					
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)					
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)					
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?					
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organised and presented in a logical order?					
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?					
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?					
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?					
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?					
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?					
Are all references in the document included in the references section?					
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of					

text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)					
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?					
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?					
Are the methods and means correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Document accepted; no changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Document accepted; changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5

8.2 Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Marie Claire Tonna

Organisation: FBA

Date: 2/12/20

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	x				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?					
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	x				
... contain a version table?	x				
... contain an updated table of contents?	x				
... contain a list of figures?	x				
... contain a list of tables?	x				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	x				
... contain an Executive Summary?	x				
... contain a Conclusions section?	x				

... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?			x		
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	x				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	x				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes))		x			
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)			x		
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	x				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	x				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organised and presented in a logical order?	x				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	x				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	x				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	x				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		x			
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		x			
Are all references in the document included in the references section?			x		
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		x			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?					

Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?	x				
Are the methods and means correctly explained?	x				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?				Thorough with great examples and data to indicate facts.	
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?				none	
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.				Great work!	

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

	Document accepted; no changes required.
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x	Document accepted; changes required.
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Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.
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 Using a half point scale.
 Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
									x